

A PROSPECTIVE STUDY ON FUNCTIONAL OUTCOME OF SURGICAL MANAGEMENT OF DISTAL RADIUS FRACTURE WITH VOLAR LOCKING PLATE

Dr. Siva Vignesh S ¹, Dr. Somejoy Moitra ²,
Dr. Hari Sivanandan ³ and Dr. M Shebin Christin I ⁴

¹ Junior Resident, Department of Orthopaedics, Vinayaka Mission's Kirupananda Variyar Medical College & Hospitals, Vinayaka Mission's Research Foundation (Deemed to be University) Salem, Tamil Nadu, India.

² Consultant Orthopaedician, Department of Orthopaedics, Vinayaka Mission's Kirupananda Variyar Medical College & Hospitals, Vinayaka Mission's Research Foundation (Deemed to be University) Salem, Tamil Nadu, India.

³ Professor, Department of Orthopaedics, Vinayaka Mission's Kirupananda Variyar Medical College & Hospitals, Vinayaka Mission's Research Foundation (Deemed to be University) Salem, Tamil Nadu, India.

⁴ Senior Resident, Department of Orthopaedics, Vinayaka Mission's Kirupananda Variyar Medical College & Hospitals, Vinayaka Mission's Research Foundation (Deemed to be University) Salem, Tamil Nadu, India.

DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.11407467](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11407467)

Abstract

Purpose: To assess the clinical and functional outcome of fracture distal radius treated with volar locking plate and to observe the complications associated with volar locking plate of distal radius.

Methodology: This is a prospective study of the functional outcome of surgical management of distal radius fracture with a volar locking plate. The study was conducted in the department of Orthopaedic Surgery at VMKV Medical College and Hospitals, Salem, from November 2020 to November 2022. Based on the study inclusion and exclusion criteria, a total of 30 cases who sustained fractures of the lower end of the radius were included in the study. All the fractures were approached by the volar approach & with 2.7mm, Fixed angle internal fixation is done with Volar Locking Plate. Volar locking plate with screws in a different direction is specially designed to buttress the distal radius. Follow-up of patients was done at six weeks, three months and six months, one year following the surgery. The final functional outcome was evaluated by the QUICK DASH evaluation questionnaire. **Results:** At the final functional assessment, we achieved an excellent outcome in 90% of cases, a good outcome in 6.66%, and a satisfactory outcome in 3.33% of cases. **Conclusion:** A satisfactory functional outcome can be obtained for a great majority of patients with most of the distal radius fractures treated with a volar locking plate.

Keywords: Wrist Fractures, Long-term Outcome, Plate, k-wire, Frykman, Prwe.

INTRODUCTION

Distal radius fractures (DRFs) are one of the most common fractures encountered in emergency care units and outpatient clinics and constitute 15–21% of all fractures¹. An apparent bimodal incidence with children under 15 years and adults over 50 at the greatest fracture risk has been described. ² Falling onto an outstretched hand is the one of the common causes for distal radius fracture; high-velocity trauma such as motor vehicle accidents, a fall from a height and contact sports and are other aetiological factors.³

Figure 1 - Etiology of distal radius fractures

In addition, osteoporosis has proven to be a significant risk factor for distal radial fracture and is the third most common location of osteoporosis related fracture in the elderly group 1,4.

The incidence curve differed in women and men: the incidence among women was more than four-fold that among men, while the incidence rate was higher among boys as children and teenagers in the 10–19 age group after 60 yrs of age. 5 (figure 2)

Figure 2. Mean annual incidence rates of DRF per 100,000 person/years by age groups, stratified by gender, 2015-2019. 5

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Open reduction and Internal fixation with a Volar Locking Plate, was performed in VMKV medical college and Hospitals, Salem. All the fractures were approached by volar approach & fixed with 2.7mm Fixed angle. Volar locking plate with screws in different direction are specially designed to buttress the distal radius. On a radiolucent table patient was positioned supine with arm by side. Image intensifier was positioned under the arm so as to visualise the distal radius, distal ulna and the articular surface to check the reduction and also for screw placement.

All procedures were performed under general or regional anaesthesia (supraclavicular or interscalene block). Our standard practice was preoperative prophylactic intravenous cefperazone + sulbactam and usage of diathermy for homeostasis.

The standard volar approach named Henry Approach was used in most of the cases to address the distal radius fragments. Skin incision made just medial to radial artery at the wrist level which lies in subcutaneous plane, can be felt. The plane is in-between the radial artery and the flexor carpi radialis. For the intermediate column fragment under the lunate facet, plane between the flexor carpi radialis tendon and the median nerve termed extended volar carpal approach, either of which is used routinely.

The pronator quadratus was erased from its lateral attachment and lifted towards ulnarside. Open reduction was performed using intrafocal leverage, traction, and temporary fixation with Kirschner wires followed by definitive fixation with the implants of choice. In cases which had a displaced radial styloid or fragments too small for other means of fixation,

was fixed with Kirschner wires and buttressed with Volar Locking Plate.

Photograph 1: Intra-operative fluoroscopy images of volar-plating

Open reduction and internal fixation with volar Locking compression plate and 2.7 mm screws were used in all our study patients, since all are intraarticular fractures with varying degree of comminution. These screws had better purchase in the distal radial comminuted fragment with poor bone stock.

Photograph 2: Surgical procedure - Henry's approach

Photograph 3: Intra-operative C-arm guided images

A period of four weeks immobilization in above elbow cast is followed as post operative protocol.

Photograph 4: Immediate post-operative limb elevation

Postop Protocol

All of them started with I.V intravenous ceferazone + sulbactam during induction which was continued for 5 days post operatively then converted into oral antibiotic clindamycin 300mg B.D. for 1 week. The hand and forearm were initially placed in a compressive dressing and elevated for forty-eight to seventy-two hours to reduce swelling. All patients were encouraged to begin an early active range of motion of the wrist and hand as tolerated by patient. Sutures were removed on the fourteenth post-operative day. Patients were not allowed to lift heavy weight for twelve to sixteen weeks but wrist mobilization, hand grip strengthening exercises and rehabilitation were vigorously initiated.

Follow up

Follow-up of patients was done at six weeks, three months and six months, one year following the surgery.

Assessment

For all subjects, radiographs were performed at the end of six weeks, three months and six months, one year follow-up. Patients are evaluated based on the following parameters at the time of discharge and all the four follow ups;

Range of Motion:

Wrist - Flexion, extension, supination, pronation, ulnar deviation and Radial deviation
Elbow - Flexion, extension, supination and pronation. Final outcome was evaluated by QUICK DASH evaluation questionnaire which consists of 11 items to measure the patient's physical function and symptoms in Upper limb.

Photograph 5: Pre-operative, post-operative and Follow up X-ray images

Photograph 6: Images depicting range of movements at follow up

RESULTS

This study is a prospective study which was conducted in the Department of Orthopaedics, . From November 2020 to November 2022. A total of 30 cases who sustained fractures of lower end of radius were included in the study as per the inclusion and exclusison criteria.

Table 1: Distribution of Sample based on Age

AGE IN YEARS	NO OF CASES	PERCENTAGE
18 – 30	6	20
31 – 40	10	33.3
41 – 50	7	23.3
51 – 60	6	20
61 – 70	1	3.3

Graph 1

Table 2: Distribution of sample based on gender

SEX	NO OF CASES	PERCENTAGE
MALE	19	63.3
FEMALE	11	36.7

Graph 2

Table 3: Distribution of the Sample based on Side of Involvement

SIDE	NO OF CASES	PERCENTAGE
RIGHT	18	60%
LEFT	12	40%

Graph 3

Table 4 : Distribution of sample based on Mode of Injury

MODE OF INJURY	NO OF CASES	PERCENTAGE
FALL ON AN OUT STRECHED HAND	28	93.33
RTA	2	6.67

Graph 4

Table 5: Fracture type based on Frykman's Classification

TYPE	NO OF CASES	PERCENTAGE
I	3	10
II	1	3.33
III	6	20
IV	5	16.66
V	5	16.66
VI	2	6.66
VII	5	16.66
VIII	3	10

Graph 5

Table 6: Distribution of Sample based on Functional Outcome Quick Dash Questionnaire

Quick Dash Score	NO OF CASES	PERCENTAGE	RESULT
0-5	27	90	Excellent
6-15	2	6.66	Good
15-30	1	3.33	Satisfactory
≥30	-	-	Poor

Graph 6

DISCUSSION

Distal radius fractures are most frequently seen upper extremity fractures. The main aim of its treatment is the re-establishment of anatomic integrity and to maintain inter-articular integrity and the radial length. The primary goal in treatment of this injury is to provide good reduction and immediate stability to achieve anatomic fracture union, allow the quick return of hand function, and avoid complications. Healing of a fracture depends on a minimal gap, adequate stability, and sufficient blood supply.

Most fractures of the distal radius are dorsally-angulated and displaced, the dorsal surface the most appropriate for buttress plating as it counteracts the deforming forces. But the disadvantages of dorsal plating (subcutaneous with hardly any soft-tissue cover, added complexity to the operation due to comminution of the dorsal cortex, the dorsal surface of the

distal radius is being convex, the extensor tendons rub against plate leading to tenosynovitis and or their rupture and loss of palmar flexion because of dorsal scarring, and early removal of the metalwork did not necessarily prevent such complications) outweighs the potential benefits (application of plate on the unstable side making it a stable construct, subcutaneous surface making easier surgical access).

To achieve optimum results functionally the distal end radius fractures, need anatomical reduction restoring the angles. There are variety of surgical management options, but in this study, we choose open reduction and internal fixation with volar plate as the modality of treatment.

Intra-articular incongruity has been shown to cause post-traumatic arthritis as described in a study conducted by Baker et al., while a study conducted by Gartland et al. malalignment can lead to decreased grip strength, reduced range of motion and instability. According some studies like that done by Leung F, Tu YK et al.⁵³ internal fixation results in a better restoration and preservation of radial length and volar tilt compared with external fixation.

In our series around 93% of patients were due to RTA and the remaining around 6% are due to fall on an outstretched hand in patients with individuals who are mostly with osteoporosis, which was comparable to F. Fitoussi & SP Chow.

Photograph 7: X-ray of an Elderly patient with osteoporosis and sustained distal radius fracture⁴⁵

This increased nature of RTA injury and involvement of younger age group is seen in our study. In our study only 3 of 30 cases (10%) are type I distal radius fractures of **Frykman's Classification**, which explains the more and more complex presentation of these fracture patterns. Most fracture patterns in our study were type III (**Frykman's Classification**) of about 20% of cases.

The average age of 40.7 years in our study with the youngest patient being 18 years and the oldest being 62 years is comparable to Jupiter *et al.* and Louis Catalanolll46 who had an average age of 43 & 30 respectively. In other studies, conducted by Kilic A *et al*47, Chung KC *et al*48, Lozano- Calderon sa *et al*49 and Anakwe E *et al*50 who reported an average age of 45 years, 48.9 years, 51 years and 48 years respectively the average age of the patients is more.

Our study had a male preponderance with 19 cases of 30 cases [63.3%] and is comparable to F Fitoussi51 & SP Chow *et al.* and Orbay J *et al.* Mode of trauma due to RTA (93.33%) is more as compare to RTA 15 (6.67%). Right side (60%) is involved more as compare to left (40%). The fixed angled 2.7mm volar locking plates was used in all our patients, with maximum number of screws in the metaphyseal region in the desired direction of anchorage.

The radiological outcome in our study is within acceptable criteria. Clinical outcome in view of wrist range of motion and grip strength are also satisfactory. The total functional result on the basis of QUICK DASH. Regarding the functional outcome in our study, we achieved an excellent outcome in 90% of cases, a good outcome in 6.66% of cases, and satisfactory outcome in 3.33% of cases, comparable to studies conducted with other authors like that done by Kenny Kwan *et al.* which showed excellent outcome in 88% of cases of a good outcome in 8% of cases based on Quick dash questionnaire.

At 3months from the procedure, clinical results, functional outcome assessed based on QUICK-DASH Questionnaire52 seem to have no significant difference at long term follow up done at 6 months and 1year. Concerning complications in our study, all 30 patients were free of any complications. None of the patients in this study developed wrist joint or small joint, hand stiffness which remains the major problem with conservative treatment with the cast

CONCLUSION

Results of this study, conclude that:

- To achieve good functional outcome and to avoid complication of prolonged immobilization, early primary fixation of DRF with volar locking plate is essential
- It facilitates early return to activities of daily living when treated with fixed angle volar locking plate patients with unstable, either volar or dorsally displaced fractures of distal radius had excellent or good fictional outcome.
- With a stable DRUJ after fixation of distal Radius fractures by means of angle stable volar locking plate it showed that it maintains DRUJ stability.
- Patients with persistent DRUJ insatiability were first stabilized with radioulnar trans fixation wire for about 4 weeks period. Then it is removed and then vigorous wrist mobilization resulted in good functional outcome.
- However, to further validate our findings long term follow-up is needed.

References

- 1) Olech J, Ciszewski M, Morasiewicz P. Epidemiology of distal radius fractures in children and adults during the COVID-19 pandemic - a twocenter study. *BMC Musculoskelet Disord*. 2021 Mar 26;22(1):306. doi: 10.1186/s12891-021-04128-5. PMID: 33771142; PMCID: PMC7995382.
- 2) Azad A., Kang H.P., Alluri R.K., Vakhshori V., Kay H.F., Ghiassi A. Epidemiological and Treatment Trends of Distal Radius Fractures across Multiple Age Groups. *J. Wrist Surg*. 2019;8:305–311. doi: 10.1055/s-0039- 1685205.
- 3) Dr. Pappu Marandi and Dr. Rahul Kumar Chandan. A comparative study of volar plate fixation versus percutaneous Kirschner wire fixation in the management of distal radius fracture in adults. *International Journal of Orthopaedics Sciences* 2019; 5(4): 553-556
- 4) Court-Brown C.M., Caesar B. Epidemiology of Adult Fractures: A Review. *Injury*. 2006;37:691–697. doi: 10.1016/j.injury.2006.04.130.
- 5) Raudasoja L, Aspinen S, Vastamäki H, Ryhänen J, Hulkkonen S. Epidemiology and Treatment of Distal Radius Fractures in Finland-A Nationwide Register Study. *J Clin Med*. 2022 May 18;11(10):2851. doi: 10.3390/jcm11102851. PMID: 35628978; PMCID: PMC9143261. 75
- 6) Denju Osada, Shuzo Kamei, Koichiro Masuzaki, Morimitsu Takai, Masahiro Kameda, Kazuya Tamai. Prospective Study of Distal Radius Fractures Treated With a Volar Locking Plate System, *The Journal of Hand Surgery*, Volume 33, Issue 5, 2008, Pages 691-700.
- 7) Pichon, H., Martin des Pallières, T., Rubens Duval, B., Carpentier, E., & Saragaglia, D. (2007). Ostéosynthèse antérieure par plaque à tête de vis verrouillée DRP 2.4 dans les fractures à déplacement postérieur de l'extrémité distale du radius. A propos de 22 cas [Using the DRP 2.4 device for volar plating of distal radius for dorsally displaced wrist fractures. Report of 22 cases]. *Chirurgie de la main*, 26(3), 127–135. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.main.2007.03.003>
- 8) Arora R, Gabl M, Erhart S, Schmidle G, Dallapozza C, Lutz M. Aspects of current management of distal radius fractures in the elderly individuals. *Geriatr Orthop Surg Rehabil*. 2011;2(5-6):187-194. doi:10.1177/2151458511426874
- 9) Dr. Pappu Marandi, Dr. Rahul Kumar Chandan. A comparative study of volar plate fixation versus percutaneous Kirschner wire fixation in the management of distal radius fracture in adults. *Int J Orthop Sci* 2019;5(4):553-556. DOI: 10.22271/ortho.2019.v5.i4j.1733
- 10) Egol, K., Walsh, M., Tejwani, N., McLaurin, T., Wynn, C., & Paksima, N. (2008). Bridging external fixation and supplementary Kirschner-wire fixation versus volar locked plating for unstable fractures of the distal radius: a randomised, prospective trial. *The Journal of bone and joint surgery. British volume*, 90(9), 1214–1221. <https://doi.org/10.1302/0301-620X.90B9.20521> 76
- 11) Esposito, J., Schemitsch, E. H., Saccone, M., Sternheim, A., & Kuzyk, P. R. (2013). External fixation versus open reduction with plate fixation for distal radius fractures: a meta-analysis of randomised controlled trials. *Injury*, 44(4), 409–416. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.injury.2012.12.003>
- 12) Ochen Y, Peek J, van der Velde D, et al. Operative vs Nonoperative Treatment of Distal Radius Fractures in Adults: A Systematic Review and Meta-analysis. *JAMA Netw Open*. 2020;3(4):e203497. doi:10.1001/jamanetworkopen.2020.3497
- 13) Zengin EC, Ozcan C, Aslan C, Bulut T, Sener M. Cast immobilization versus volar locking plate fixation of AO type C distal radial fractures in patients aged 60 years and older. *Acta Orthop Traumatol Turc*. 2019;53(1):15-18. doi:10.1016/j.aott.2018.10.005
- 14) van Leerdam RH, Huizing F, Termaat F, et al. Patient-reported outcomes after a distal radius fracture in adults: a 3-4 years follow-up. *Acta Orthop*. 2019;90(2):129-134. doi:10.1080/17453674.2019.1568098
- 15) Handoll, H. H., & Madhok, R. (2003). Surgical interventions for treating distal radial fractures in adults. *The Cochrane database of systematic reviews*, (3), CD003209. <https://doi.org/10.1002/14651858.CD003209>
- 16) Thomas W. Wright, MaryBeth Horodyski, Dean W. Smith. Functional outcome of unstable distal radius fractures: ORIF with a volar fixed-angle tine plate versus external fixation. *The Journal of Hand Surgery*. Volume 30, Issue 2, 2005. Pages 289-299.77

- 17) Woolnough, T., Axelrod, D., Bozzo, A., Koziarz, A., Koziarz, F., Oitment, C., Gyemi, L., Gormley, J., Gouveia, K., & Johal, H. (2021). What Is the Relative Effectiveness of the Various Surgical Treatment Options for Distal Radius Fractures? A Systematic Review and Network Meta-analysis of Randomized Controlled Trials. *Clinical orthopaedics and related research*, 479(2), 348–362.
- 18) Obert L, Loisel F, Gasse N, Lepage D. Distal radius anatomy applied to the treatment of wrist fractures by plate: a review of recent literature. *SICOT J*. 2015;1:14. Published 2015 Jun 19. doi:10.1051/sicotj/2015012
- 19) Drake RL et al, editors: Grays atlas of anatomy, ed 2, Philadelphia, 2015, Churchill Livingstone
- 20) Hazani, Ron & Engineer, Nitin & Cooney, Damon & Wilhelmi, Bradon. (2008). Anatomic Landmarks for the First Dorsal Compartment. *Eplasty*. 8. e53.
- 21) Junyalmatani, KeiichiAkita, KumikoYamaguchi, HirotakaShimizu, HidenoriKondou, ToshifumiOzaki. An Anatomical Study of the Watershed Line on the Volar, Distal Aspect of the Radius: Implications for Plate Placement and Avoidance of Tendon Ruptures *The Journal of Hand Surgery* Volume 37, Issue 8, August 2012, Pages 1550-1554
- 22) Egol K et al. *Handbook of Fractures*. Philadelphia:Wolters Kluwer; 2015: 266-27878
- 23) Petron, DJ. Distal Radius Fractures in Adults. In: UpToDate, Post TW (Ed), UpToDate, Waltham, MA. (Accessed on June 8th, 2016)
- 24) DeAngelis MA, Wald DA. Wrist. In: Sherman SC. eds. *Simon's Emergency Orthopedics*, 7e. New York, NY: McGraw-Hill; 2014.
- 25) Shehovych A, Salar O, Meyer C, Ford DJ. Adult distal radius fractures classification systems: essential clinical knowledge or abstract memory testing?. *Ann R Coll Surg Engl*. 2016;98(8):525-531. doi:10.1308/rcsann.2016.0237